

The Use of Home Mechanical Ventilation during Pregnancy; Case Report of Three Women

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ABSTRACT/BACKGROUND

Chronic hypercapnic respiratory failure is a recognised complication of a range of medical conditions, including; neuromuscular disorders, obesity hypoventilation syndrome, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases and restrictive thoracic diseases^[1,2]. In order to improve ventilation and reduce pCO₂ levels patients are assessed for long term non-invasive home mechanical ventilation (HMV). The estimated prevalence of HMV is 7.3/100 000 population^[2]. Included in this patient cohort are women of childbearing age, with conditions such as muscular dystrophy, Pompe's and kyphoscoliosis^[3, 4]. During pregnancy changes such as marked abdominal distension, may precipitate acute hypoxic and/or hypercapnic respiratory failure in individuals who are already high risk for developing respiratory failure^[5]. Acute non-invasive ventilation (NIV) is a recognised treatment for this complication and mask ventilation can be initiated during delivery should respiratory distress develop in an at-risk patient^[5]. Whilst the use of acute-NIV in at risk patients during childbirth is established^[5] there are no guidelines on managing patients on HMV who wish to become pregnant. There are case reports of women established on HMV having successful pregnancies^[4, 5, 6, 7], however there is little reported on the patients' perspectives or experiences of HMV during pregnancy.

Keywords: Pregnancy; Women; Home mechanical ventilation

CASE SERIES

We describe the cases of three women who used HMV prior to conception, during their pregnancies and in one case during their delivery. We interviewed the three women on their experiences and perceptions of pregnancy whilst using HMV.

Case 1: 36 years old woman with a diagnosis of Pompe's disease. First pregnancy. Patient was established on long term HMV prior to conception and used HMV throughout pregnancy. She used her domiciliary bipap machine throughout labour.

Case 2: 39 years old with a diagnosis of kyphoscoliosis. Patient had 3 previous pregnancies and gave birth under

general anaesthetic for all three. 18 months after her third pregnancy she became unwell and was admitted to intensive care, during this admission she was commenced on long term HMV. She had difficulties using her HMV during pregnancy. She was motivated to comply with treatment but struggled to tolerate it. The decision was made by the doctors that she should give birth under general anaesthetic and be admitted to the intensive care unit following delivery for a period of observation. She resumed HMV after her delivery.

Case 3: 32 years old with a diagnosis of kyphoscoliosis. Second pregnancy. Previous delivery with a general anaesthetic and patient commenced on long term HMV following her first pregnancy. Initially she was given an epidural and no ventilation support. She failed to progress with the epidural and she was subsequently given a general anaesthetic.

PATIENT EXPERIENCES

The three women we interviewed had a range of experiences prior to conception, during their pregnancies and after giving birth. All three women discussed the possibility of pregnancy with their home ventilation teams prior to conception. One woman reported that her respiratory consultant had advised against her becoming pregnant due to the risks of pregnancy whilst using HMV. This resulted in her delaying her second pregnancy by 9 years, at which point her care was taken over by a new respiratory consultant. When she discussed the possibility of pregnancy with her new consultant, she felt 'supported' in her decision to become pregnant. The other two women recalled discussing pregnancy with their home ventilation teams, their perceptions of their teams' reactions were described as 'amazing', 'reassured' and 'good'. One woman reported difficulties with using her HMV machine during her pregnancy. She described feeling 'patronised' and receiving 'judgemental' care from the ventilation team because she was unable to use her HMV machine for prolonged periods of time. She was unable to tolerate the machine settings and felt she did not receive support in finding ways to address this. This had a significant impact on her mental wellbeing during her pregnancy. Despite this over all she felt she received 'excellent care' and all women felt 'completely' supported by their respiratory consultants during their pregnancies. All three women were positive about their experience of pregnancy whilst being long term HMV users. When asked if they had advice for women in a similar position they responded 'go for it'. They advised women to 'speak to someone who has done it' in order to gain insight into some of the difficulties faced and the possibilities of what pregnancy and giving birth on HMV might involve, such as; the difficulty of not all medical teams involved in the pregnancy being familiar with HMV or the possibility of giving birth using domiciliary machines rather than under a general anaesthetic. One woman commented that her birth plan wasn't discussed with her that her medical team 'insisted on a general anaesthetic' and in hindsight she would have liked to explore giving birth whilst using HMV. Possibly speaking to another HMV user who had used HMV during labour may have given her more insight into what this may have involved and empowered her to discuss it with her obstetric and ventilation teams and ensured she had autonomy over the decisions being made.

DISCUSSION

Increasing numbers of patients are being commenced on domiciliary HMV and this can affect women of childbearing age^[8,9]. It is important for home ventilation teams to be able to support women on long term HMV wishing to start a

family. All three patients were established on long term HMV before becoming pregnant. Whilst using their HMV in pregnancy the patients had very diverse experiences; ranging from feeling fully supported and as though the decision was ‘up to me’ ‘never told you can’t’ to feeling ‘patronised’ and receiving ‘judgemental care’. Ventilation teams need to ensure women who use HMV are supported in their life choices, including decisions regarding pregnancy. The practical and holistic care needed for HMV is significantly increased when the patient is pregnant. The positive experience reported by our patients shows what a positive impact the ventilation team can have in empowering patients to make informed decisions for themselves.

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